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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D2.4 (D8):

Co-creating strategies for navigating multilevel policy dynamics to encourage SIE – reflections

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Executive Summary

Social innovation is increasingly being recognised in policy making on different levels. However, to harness its full potential for accelerating sustainable energy transitions it is important to understand how policies impact diverse types of social innovation in energy. Therefore, Deliverable 8 provides guidance on how to better connect with and harness policy dynamics at different governance levels that are of relevance for social innovation in energy. This is done by offering reflections on a multi-level, multi-actor policy dialogue facilitated with SIE intermediaries, SONNET city partners and relevant policy makers from all governance levels. During the policy-dialogue, participants discussed how to better consider social innovation in energy in the proposed Fit for 55 package.

The insights and reflections synthesized in this deliverable culminate in action points for socially innovative actors and their intermediaries as well as policy makers and researchers on how to better connect with and harness policy dynamics at different governance levels. It builds on a policy mix synopsis of SONNET's case studies of diverse types of social innovation in energy and a policy dialogue that took place online on 14 January 2022 as part of ICLEI's Breakfast at Sustainability's event series. The dialogue brought together policy makers, advocacy groups and researchers to discuss opportunities and challenges for an enhanced consideration of social innovation in energy with a focus on the EU's Fit for 55 package, as well as implications for other governance levels. The ultimate aim of the dialogue was to generate overarching reflections on how social innovation in energy can be better harnessed by EU policy making, and in policy making at all levels.

Part 1 lays out the foundations needed to explore the opportunities and challenges of integrating social innovation in the Fit for 55 package, with a focus on how doing so can accelerate sustainable energy transitions in Europe. It introduces the 'diversity of social innovation in energy' and 'policy mix thinking' in the context of social innovation, and provides insights on how policy mixes have been influencing four types of social innovation in energy.

Part 2 provides a report of the policy dialogue we organised to discuss the following questions: What role does social innovation in energy play in the 'Fit for 55' package, and how could this role be enhanced? What challenges do policy makers and advocacy groups face when working to translate interest in social innovation into concrete policy action, and how could these be overcome? The event brought together SIE intermediaries, SONNET city partners and relevant policy makers from all governance levels discussing strategies for enhancing the role of SIE in EU, national, regional and local energy policy making. It included two speakers from the SONNET project, and five panellists with expertise in social innovation in energy – ranging from the EU DG Research & Innovation and DG Energy to ICLEI Europe, Friends of the Earth Europe and Rescoop.eu.

Finally, based on the insights gained during the dialogue and validated in a SONNET city partner workshop part 3 reports key reflections and provides action points that can be seen as way forward in better considering social innovation in energy and climate policy making. They include:

Priority area 1: Energy and climate policy maker's awareness of, and willingness to engage with social innovation in energy

1. Raise awareness for social innovation across energy and climate policy makers.
2. Connect with key policy actors who are drafting energy and climate policy proposals.
3. Adopt policy mix thinking across energy, climate and innovation policies for governing the emergence, upscaling and diffusion of social innovation in energy.

Priority area 2: Defining and conceptualizing social innovation in energy transitions

4. Sharpen the definition of social innovation in energy used by policy makers.
5. Adopt both a broad definition of social innovation in energy in general, which can be complemented by specific definitions of key types.
6. Devise long-term policy strategies specifying the foreseen role of social innovation in energy transitions.

Priority area 3: Benefits and impacts of, and metrics for social innovation in energy

7. Take stock and synthesize existing assessment and evaluation practices for determining the impact of social innovation in energy.
8. Ensure that future policy impact assessments and policy evaluations incorporate social innovation as one of its dimensions.
9. Improve future policy support for social innovation in energy based on evidence from impact assessments and policy evaluations.

Priority area 4: Multi-level governance and the role of the local level for supporting social innovation in energy

10. Provide clear EU-level guidance for policy makers on other levels regarding the beneficial role of social innovation in energy transitions.
11. Ensure consistency between EU and national policies relevant for social innovation in energy.
12. Include the perspective of cities in EU energy and climate policy making due to their proximity to socially innovative initiatives in energy.

Table of Contents

This deliverable consists of three different parts, which are meant as standalone documents. The separate parts might include additional, more detailed tables of contents.

Part 1: Briefing	1
Part 2: Event report	26
Part 3: Reflections	44
Appendix: EC summary requirements	67

Figures

Figure 1-1: Snapshot of SONNET's typology of social innovation in energy	6
Figure 1-2: Consideration of social innovation in the Fit for 55 package	7
Figure 1-3: 'Policy mix thinking' for social innovation	9
Figure 2-1: Graphic harvest of the presentations given at the policy dialogue	29
Figure 2-2: Graphic harvest of the Q&A session at the policy dialogue	43
Figure 3-1: Reflections on enhancing the role of social innovation in energy in policy making	49

PART 1: BRIEFING

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SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY MEETS THE FIT FOR 55 PACKAGE

Policy opportunities and challenges

BRIEFING in advance of the SONNET policy dialogue, hosted as part of the *Breakfast at Sustainability's* event series, on 14 January 2022.

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February 2022

Social Innovation in Energy Transitions: co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potential of social innovation to transform energy systems.

Please note that this briefing paper was sent to all participants of the policy dialogue prior to the event; therefore, it refers to the event as something occurring in the future.

Preface

What role does social innovation in energy play in the 'Fit for 55' package, and how could this role be enhanced? What challenges do policy makers and advocacy groups face when working to translate interest in social innovation into concrete policy action, and how could these be overcome?

On 14 January 2022, the **S**ocial **I**nnovation in **E**nergy **T**ransitions project ([SONNET](#)) is bringing local and European policy makers, advocacy groups and researchers together to explore these questions. Ultimately, it is our aim that this event helps to better harness the potential of social innovation in policy, including in the European Union's Fit for 55 package.

In this briefing paper, we lay the foundations needed to explore the opportunities and challenges of integrating social innovation in the Fit for 55 package, with a focus on how doing so can accelerate sustainable energy transitions in Europe.

First, participants are introduced to the concept of social innovation and its diversity in the energy sector (section [1](#)). This is followed by an introduction to the Fit for 55 package, and foreseen links to social innovation based on current policy proposals (section [2](#)). The briefing then introduces 'policy mix thinking' in the context of social innovation (section [3](#)), and provides insights on how policy mixes have been influencing four types of social innovation in energy (section [4](#)).

The briefing also presents questions that will guide the policy dialogue. Panellists will offer their perspectives on these questions, and will discuss strategies to enhance the role of social innovation in the Fit for 55 package (section [5](#)). Finally, the briefing includes the event agenda (section [6](#)) and panellists' bios (section [7](#)).

We hope this briefing document provides a solid basis for a stimulating and rich exchange of ideas at the policy dialogue. Furthermore, it is our hope that the briefing, policy dialogue event, and a summary report to be published after the dialogue catalyse further discussions on better integrating social innovation throughout the Fit for 55 policy making process. The summary report will, in particular, draw on insights from the policy dialogue to derive overarching reflections on how social innovation in energy can be better harnessed by EU policy making, and in policy making at all levels.

The SONNET project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 837498.

Table of Contents for Briefing

1	Introduction to social innovation in energy and its diversity	5
2	Introduction to the 'Fit for 55' package and its link to social innovation	7
3	Introduction to policy mix thinking in the context of social innovation	9
4	Relevance of policy mix for social innovation in energy: SONNET examples.....	13
	4.1 Cooperative energy production and consumption.....	13
	4.2 Participatory incubation and experimentation	15
	4.3 Local electricity exchange	17
	4.4 Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways	19
5	Motivation and guiding questions for policy dialogue.....	21
6	Agenda for the policy dialogue	22
7	Speaker Bios.....	23
8	Further information	25

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1 INTRODUCTION TO SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY AND ITS DIVERSITY

The [SONNET](#) project investigates the diversity of social innovation in energy transitions. We are interested in analysing new ways of *doing, thinking* and/or *organising* energy. This can include new ways of generating, distributing or consuming energy, as well as new framings that change the way we think about energy. In other words, 'social innovation' for SONNET includes both changes in social practices, as well as changes in societal discourses, such as changes in how we view using new technologies to share energy locally. In all cases, at the heart of SONNET's definition of social innovation in energy are *changes in social relations*, e.g. new collaborations or competition between previously unconnected actors.

Social innovation in energy (SIE) is a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy.

SONNET's broad understanding of social innovation in energy acknowledges that such innovation goes beyond the classic examples of cooperative energy production and community energy, and also includes less often discussed examples like new financing mechanisms, campaigns for clean energy pathways, or new ways of exchanging electricity locally. Furthermore, SONNET acknowledges that social innovation also includes rediscovering old practices, and finding new ways to combine existing ideas, objects and/or actions.

To better understand this diversity of social innovation in energy, SONNET created a [typology](#), which is structured along two dimensions (see Figure 1-1). The first dimension concerns the type of social relations (cooperation, exchange, competition, conflict):

- **Cooperation:** when people jointly work together to achieve a shared goal
- **Exchange:** voluntary interaction from which all parties expect to benefit
- **Competition:** when actors struggle over scarce resources, regulated by shared rules
- **Conflict:** unregulated struggle over scarce resources; may include attempts to 'neutralise' the opposition

The [typology](#)'s second dimension captures types of energy activities (doing, thinking, and organising energy):

- **Doing:** practices related to energy technologies and the physical composition of the energy system (e.g. the act of building a new wind turbine or installing solar PV)
- **Thinking:** forms of knowledge and normative framings including values and perceptions (e.g. energy education, peer-to-peer learning, framings against specific energy pathways).
- **Organising:** new governance and organisational structures within initiatives and within the energy system (e.g. participatory energy dialogues, platforms for direct energy transactions, etc.).

Figure 1-1: Snapshot of SONNET's typology of social innovation in energy; Source: SONNET Energy Read #1, illustrations by Maria Fraaije

Consideration of social innovation in the Fit for 55 package

The Fit for 55 package aims to encourage transformational change by creating “new opportunities for innovation”ⁱⁱⁱ. However, the policy proposals included in the Fit for 55 package largely under-recognise social innovation. Indeed, a keyword search¹ reveals that the term 'social innovation' is not mentioned as such in the proposals, apart from once in the Renovation Wave.

Some policy proposals do refer to specific types of social innovation in energy: the potential of renewable energy cooperatives is recognised and directly addressed as part of the foreseen revisions of the Energy Efficiency Directive and the Renewable Energy Directive; and novel forms of for-profit services and technologies, innovative financing mechanisms, consulting and energy education are all mentioned. However, some prominent types of social innovation appear to be neglected completely, such as gamification or the role of peer-to-peer learning. Even in the cases where social innovations are noted, their recognition tends to be limited to mentions in only a few policy proposals – most often the Energy Efficiency Directive and/or the Renewable Energy Directive, followed by the Social Climate Fund.

As such, social innovation is partly recognised as important for creating acceptance for decarbonisation, particularly in the context of clean energy transitions. However, the full potential of social innovation does not seem to be harnessed yet, including its contributions to addressing energy poverty, enhancing energy democracy, empowering citizens and ensuring just energy transitions. If left unchanged, this would represent a missed opportunity to support the achievement of the EU's 55% reduction target. The required system changes needed to meet that target are socio-technical and call for both technological *and* social innovation.

¹ The conducted keyword search included terms related to different types of social innovation. Furthermore, we used more general keywords trying to capture "social innovation" with a broader approach.

3 INTRODUCTION TO POLICY MIX THINKING IN THE CONTEXT OF SOCIAL INNOVATION

Figure 1-3: ‘Policy mix thinking’ for social innovation; Illustration (and its component parts, displayed in the pages that follow): Carlotta Cataldi

Policy mix thinking

To reach Europe’s target of a 55% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, new and ambitious goals must be implemented through concrete policy tools that span: tightening existing policy instruments (such as carbon emission trading), introducing new ones (such as the Social Climate Fund), and phasing-out inconsistent measures (such as tax exemptions for fossil fuels).

A ‘policy mix’ includes a policy strategy and instruments to implement this strategy. The instruments in the EU’s climate policy mix need to be adjusted so that they are aligned (i.e. consistent) with the increased ambition of the 2030 target, and thus with the EU’s climate policy strategy.

It is well-understood that accelerating climate-friendly technological innovation requires consistent policy strategies and instruments^{iv}. However, much less attention has been paid to the impact of policy mixes on social innovation. This gap can be addressed by considering the relationship between the policy mix and social innovation using both a *top-down* and a *bottom-up* approach^v.

Top down: What is the EU's policy mix for social innovation?

The first approach starts by identifying the strategic intent of a policy mix; in this case, that means examining the extent to which social innovation is a strategic policy goal for the EU.

In the EU, social innovation has, since the early-2000s, been recognised as an important tool for achieving smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth, as set out in the Europe 2020 Strategy.^{vi} By 2009, the Bureau of European Policy Advisors had already done important work that put social innovation on the European policy agenda as an instrument to address societal challenges.^{vii} *In other words, the strategic importance of social innovation has been recognised by the EU.*

Over time, social innovation has also found its way into the EU's research and innovation programmes, including FP7 and Horizon 2020, and into policies by the European Social Fund.^{viii} Recent policy renewals for the funding period 2021-2027 (Horizon Europe) frame social innovation as a horizontal "key specific issue".^{iv} *Several EU policies actively support social innovation.*

The European Commission recognises the relationship between energy transition and social innovation, as demonstrated by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission's engagement with the role of social innovation for energy transitions.^{ix} Through this work and via its research and innovation programmes, it is clear that the European Commission both supports social innovation (in energy), and recognises the link between social innovation and the energy sector.

The energy sector is one sector that will be impacted by the mix of European policies that aim to promote social innovation – in other words, *the energy sector is one of the 'impact domains' of the EU's policy mix for social innovation.*

What's more, EU Member States, regions and cities may have their own, additional social innovation policy mixes with potential links to energy.

Bottom up: Which policy mix is of relevance for social innovation in energy?

As SONNET research has shown^x, different policy strategies and instruments impact diverse types of social innovation in energy, whether or not they have been intentionally implemented to promote social innovation in energy (see examples in section 4). To identify the relevant policy mix for these different social innovation types, it is important to understand – via bottom-up examination – how social innovation comes about, which actors are involved, and how policy instruments influence their activities.

Policy strategies and policy instruments at different governance levels, and which originate from different fields, can all be relevant to social innovation in energy if they: *enable or impede – intentionally or unintentionally – the development of social innovations in energy.*

More often than not, these policies originate from multiple governance levels; however, the EU level is often quite important. Not only can policies be traced back to multiple levels, but they also originate from various policy fields, with energy, climate and innovation policy typically being of primary relevance. In addition, and similarly to technological innovation^{xi}, what seems to matter most for determining the impact of these policies on social innovation is their actual design rather than the type of policy instrument.

What this means for Fit for 55

SONNET's research suggests that the *design of the policies* contained in the Fit for 55 package will determine the extent to which they will harness the full potential of social innovation.

Discussing the Fit for 55 policy proposals from the perspective of their impact on social innovation is therefore an important task in the process of further negotiating the policy proposals. For this debate, the bottom up approach may be particularly valuable to delineate policy mixes relevant for social innovation. In addition, appreciating that social innovation is shaped by the interplay of various policies, which can go beyond the Fit for 55 package, may help facilitate a coordinated design effort across policy fields and governance levels.

4 RELEVANCE OF POLICY MIX FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY: SONNET EXAMPLES

Drawing on SONNET’s research,^x this section uses four examples to illustrate the usefulness of applying bottom-up policy mix thinking to better understand the role of policies on social innovation in energy.

4.1 Cooperative energy production and consumption

Renewable energy cooperatives are models through which citizens jointly own the means of production of renewable energy (e.g. wind power plants or solar panels), while also participating in the organisation of the cooperatives. By enabling citizens to become central actors at all levels of using and producing energy, cooperatives contribute to democratisation and to a change in social relations.^{xii}

SONNET studied the innovation histories of the field of cooperative energy production and consumption in Germany, France and Switzerland.

Illustration by Maria Fraaije

Key insights on policy mixes

Supportive legal frameworks, such as feed-in tariffs, were crucial to enabling cooperative organisation of energy. SONNET’s findings further highlight the importance of predictable national energy policy support, as this consistency provides long-term investment security. While

national energy policy instruments have historically provided such predictability, national support for renewable energy cooperatives has declined substantially in all studied countries.

EU and national policies: impact of EU policies on national policies in Germany

SONNET found that the EU has been an influential driver for national support schemes in its Member States.

Germany's Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) was a critical driver of the development of renewable energy cooperatives, while later changes to the EEG became a key impeding factor to cooperatives. This and other national policies are often driven by preceding EU regulations, as was the case for the liberalisation of the German electricity market, which was based on EU directive 96/02/EC, and for the introduction of Germany's capital investment act based on EU directive 2011/61/EU. Treaty violation proceedings against the German feed-in tariffs by the European Commission further illustrate the EU's influence on national policies.

National policies: national policies in France favour large-scale cooperative projects

As in Germany, France is also characterised by a historically highly centralised energy sector. However, while Germany's feed-in tariff model also supported small-scale investments, in France support focused on large-scale projects to the detriment of small-scale energy cooperatives.

While small projects were initially supported by the feed-in tariff model, a 2017 decree made projects below 36 kWp unattractive financially, forcing cooperatives to develop larger projects. Such projects would require cooperatives to convince financial institutions of their viability. This trend continues today and cooperatives are increasingly required to develop projects that are interesting for private players.

Recent decline in policy support for renewable energy cooperatives has led to the formation and organisation of social innovators in intermediary organisations trying to more effectively represent their interests in policy making and implementation processes. For example, in Germany, energy cooperatives are organising in regional or national networks. There is also cross-country evidence that local governments are often willing, and partly able, to compensate for detrimental policy changes at the national level.

How are renewable energy cooperatives addressed in the Fit for 55 package?

Renewable energy cooperatives are the social innovation type most directly addressed and acknowledged in the Fit for 55 package. This is especially seen in the revisions of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), which clearly mention renewable (and citizen) energy communities as helpful to support the energy transition and to prevent energy poverty.

4.2 Participatory incubation and experimentation

The field of participatory incubation and experimentation refers to making use of sites of multi-actor collaboration and experimentation, like living labs, city labs, testbeds, pilots, and transition arenas. Experiments typically take place in settings that are close to real-world contexts, involving everyday problems and actors. The aim is to find new ways of organising energy production, distribution and consumption, for instance by testing new technologies, funding mechanisms or governance structures. The primary goal of these experiments is to spark innovation and to co-create new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy.^{xii}

SONNET studied the innovation histories of participatory incubation and experimentation in the Netherlands, Germany, and Poland.

Illustration by Maria Fraaije

Key insights on policy mixes

EU and national-level innovation policies play an important role for participatory incubation and experimentation, and tend to be implemented by innovation and energy departments (or related agencies). However, openness to experimentation differs across countries. While some countries (e.g. the Netherlands) are more open to, and experienced with, co-creative approaches, a more top-down policy style in other countries (e.g. Poland) acts as a barrier to supporting such co-creative, experimental formats.

EU policies: EU policies encourage 'energy clusters' in Poland

EU funding for various forms of experimentation is, of course, a key enabler. However, EU policy strategies, such as the EU climate and energy targets for 2020 and the Renewable Energy Directive from 2009, also matter, particularly in countries with lower climate mitigation ambitions. For example, in Poland the definition of 'energy clusters' was first introduced in the Polish Renewable Energy Sources Act in 2016 to bring Polish law closer to the existing laws in other EU Member States, and to help meet the climate goals set by the EU. This 'energy cluster' model furthermore helped to encourage the development of participatory and experimental formats in Poland.

National policies: R&D programmes fund transdisciplinary research in Germany

National funding instruments, whether they originate from Energy, Innovation, or other Ministries, are also critical in this field. In Germany the FONA programme (Research for Sustainability) was launched in 1999 by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research. Since then, the programme has continued to provide funding for transdisciplinary sustainability research. This laid the foundation for experimental and collaborative multi-actor formats in energy-related research and development (R&D) policies, which were later picked up by other ministries.

Funding for experimental multi-actor formats became known by the term 'Reallabore' (real world laboratories). This term first emerged in regional level R&D funding in the State of Baden-Württemberg in 2015, and was later adopted at the national level, as part of a strategy and funding programme for 'Reallabore' that was launched in 2018 by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi).

Relevant policies mainly focus on driving experimentation. Scaling-up successful experiments remains a major challenge across countries. It therefore remains uncertain whether and how learning from experiments will lead to changes in the broader policy mix.

How is participatory incubation and experimentation addressed in the Fit for 55 package?

In contrast to renewable energy cooperatives, the Fit for 55 package does not directly refer to encouraging participatory incubation and experimentation formats as a type of social innovation in energy. However, it is worth noting that this field is addressed by the Renovation Wave.

Experimentation at the *local level* is addressed by the EU, including as part of the EU mission on 'Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities', and by the New European Bauhaus initiative.

4.3 Local electricity exchange

Local electricity exchange concerns matching local renewable energy generation with local consumption. This can result in new business models and new forms of collaboration, sometimes with the goal of allowing more people to become engaged in energy transitions. The aim of local electricity exchange is to increase the share of renewable energy in current energy systems, and to reform electricity markets by maximising the use of locally-produced energy. Local electricity exchange is socially innovative as it represents a different way of generating electricity, one that happens closer to the consumer. Such local production of electricity also changes how people relate to energy.^{xii}

SONNET studied the innovation histories of the field of local electricity exchange in France, the UK, and Switzerland.

Illustration by Maria Fraaije

Key insights on policy mixes

Local electricity exchange can rely on complex technology, legalities and policies, which are often barriers for small electricity generators. SONNET's analysis shows the highly contested nature of the field, in which actors have polarised perspectives due to the disruptive potential of this social innovation in energy.

EU and national policies: complexity and lack of regulatory guidance

At present, EU-level policies do not encourage local electricity exchange, and a lack of clear and specific regulatory guidance contributes to uncertainty. Despite the lack of – and need for – more direct regulations at the EU level, the main impeding condition identified by SONNET so far pertains to national policies.

In France, for example, the legal framework surrounding collective self-consumption is extremely constraining. It requires creating a legal entity and specifies a small perimeter in which projects can take place. This makes it difficult for projects to emerge and find a business model that works.

In other countries there are some novel policy proposals which, if adopted, would enable the development of local electricity exchange. An example from the UK is the Local Electricity Bill, which aims to empower communities to sell their energy directly to local people.

National policies: differing views on the contested nature of local exchange

National energy policies tend to impede the development of local electricity exchange. This is sometimes done intentionally to avoid the disruptive potential of peer-to-peer electricity exchange. In France, policies have been designed to make sure their disruptive potential is reduced so as not to compromise the current business model of established actors.

One example is the disagreement around fair grid prices for projects of collective self-consumption. Another disagreement has arisen with some proponents of local electricity exchange contesting tariff equalisation, which is one of the guiding principles of the French electricity system. While it ensures that all French consumers pay a similar grid price, it makes it more difficult for collective self-consumption projects to generate a return on investment.

The contested nature of this social innovation can be seen differently by national policy makers. The Finance Ministry, regulatory bodies and established actors tend to try to slow down changes in order to protect a centrally-organised energy system; while the Ministry of Environment and some parliamentarians have shown more openness to changes that transfer more decision-making power to local actors, who they consider central players in the energy transition.

To overcome some of these barriers, the UK government has opted for a regulatory sandbox approach, used to experiment with innovative ideas in an environment where some of the usual regulations do not apply.

How is local electricity exchange addressed in the Fit for 55 package?

EU-level policies are criticised for not providing sufficient clarity on enabling regulations for local electricity exchange. The Fit for 55 package does not seem to tackle this regulatory uncertainty: according to a keyword search in current policy proposals, local electricity exchange is only mentioned in the Renovation Wave.

4.4 Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways

Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways can originate from different actors, including NGOs, networks, protest groups and citizen groups. The main aim of these framings is to change mainstream energy practices by influencing policymaking, stopping local fossil fuel extraction, and/or offering alternative energy future scenarios. This is done via, for example, campaigns, protests, petitions, and the sharing of information, expertise and experiences. These framings shift energy storytelling and challenge how society relates to the fossil fuel industry.^{xiii}

SONNET studied the innovation histories of the field of framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the Netherlands, Poland and the UK.

Illustration by Maria Fraaije

Key insights on policy mixes

The insufficiency of national policies to meet the Paris Agreement has become a main driver of activities around framings against fossil fuel pathways over the last five years. Inconsistent policy mixes, where policy instruments are not in line with climate policy strategies, especially trigger protests against governments' chosen energy pathways. Lack of climate policy ambition sparks activities such as demonstrating against the nationally-chosen fossil fuel pathways, attempting to influence or cooperate with policy makers and other actors at the local level, raising complaints in courts, and participating in funding programmes at different governance levels (e.g. EU just transition funds).

EU and national policies: tension between EU and Polish policies on coal phase-out

Bottom-up resistance from social movements is often motivated by national governments not doing enough to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, or even attempting – and/or succeeding – to introduce policy changes that add to the climate crisis, such as actively pursuing new fossil fuel projects.

In Poland, the national government has so far played an impeding role regarding coal phase-out, as it has been strongly supporting the fossil fuel industry. While EU policies such as the Just Transition Mechanism and the Platform on Coal Regions in Transition provide funding for the phase-out of fossil fuel energy, the Polish government has blocked some of the EU's efforts towards achieving carbon neutrality and has been postponing the coal phase-out date. As territorial just transition plans must be coherent with national energy and climate plans, this may result in a reduction of the EU transition resources for Poland.

National and local policies: policy changes as a result of SIE-activities in the Netherlands

National governments promoting the interests of fossil fuel incumbents are increasingly meeting (local) resistance. In the Netherlands, policies supporting gas extraction in the large Groningen gas field, which caused severe earthquakes, only changed significantly after 2012. These policy mix changes were driven by the establishment of an association of those impacted, who first aimed to receive compensation, and later started to fight for a “gas-free future”. In November 2020, the Minister of Economic Affairs announced a prohibition on gas extraction from the Groningen field.

Besides the Groningen case, and in relation to shale gas extractions, policy changes occurred in the National Mining Act that extend the ground of refusal to protect the environment, safety or public health, and to include a role for decentral governments in the decision-making process related to the Mining Act.

How are framings against fossil fuels addressed in the Fit for 55 package?

Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways is not referred to in policy proposals as part of the Fit for 55 package. However, the societal pressure generated by social movements criticising current policy mixes as insufficient to tackle the climate crisis may well benefit the adoption of more stringent climate and energy policies that are well-aligned with the EU's 2030 climate targets.

5 MOTIVATION AND GUIDING QUESTIONS FOR POLICY DIALOGUE

The motivation behind the policy dialogue, co-organised by the SONNET team and ICLEI's Breakfast at Sustainability's event series on 14 January 2022, is to explore opportunities and challenges to harnessing the potential of social innovation through the Fit for 55 package, in particular for the decarbonisation of the energy sector.

To do this, the policy dialogue brings together policy makers, advocacy groups and researchers to discuss the following key questions:

- **Opportunities:** What opportunities do you see for the consideration of social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package?
- **Challenges:** What challenges do you foresee that could act as barriers to considering social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package, and how might they be overcome?

By facilitating this policy dialogue, SONNET aims to generate overarching reflections on how social innovation could be better harnessed within EU energy and climate policy making, as well as at other governance levels.

6 AGENDA FOR THE POLICY DIALOGUE

9:30–9:50

Introduction: Introduction to social innovation in energy and its diversity, followed by a presentation of policy mix thinking for social innovation in energy.

Julia Wittmayer (DRIFT), **Karoline Rogge** (Fraunhofer ISI; University of Sussex)

9:50–10:45

Opportunities & Challenges: Exploring the opportunities and challenges associated with meaningfully considering social innovation in energy in the European Union’s Fit for 55 package, both from a policy perspective, and from the perspective of social innovation in energy practitioners.

Emilie Vandam (DG Research and Innovation), **Cristiana Marchitelli** (DG Energy), **Giorgia Rambelli** (ICLEI Europe), **Dimitris Tsekeris** (Friends of the Earth Europe), **Stavroula Pappa** (REScoop.eu)

Coffee break

10:55–11:40

Q&A: Moderated ‘fishbowl discussion’ to facilitate questions, answers, and dialogue amongst speakers and participants.

Moderated by the SONNET team

11:40–11:55

Reflection on discussion: Present graphic recording and discuss what may still be missing.

Moderated by the SONNET team

11:55–12:00

Wrap-up: Closing the event, next step: recommendations to policy makers.

Moderated by the SONNET team

7 SPEAKER BIOS

Julia Wittmayer leads the conceptual development around social innovation and energy in the EU funded SONNET project. She is Assistant Professor at the Erasmus School of Social and Behavioural Sciences and works as senior researcher and advisor at DRIFT. Her work focuses on social innovations in processes of transformative change and their governance in urban areas, and in the context of energy system change. To support the development of knowledge and transformative action that addresses societal challenges, she develops and implements a variety of collaborative action-oriented research formats.

Karoline Rogge is scientific coordinator of the EU funded SONNET project investigating social innovation in energy transitions (2019-2022), and leads its socio-political work package. She is Professor of Sustainability Innovation and Policy at the Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex, and Deputy Head of the competence centre Society and Policy at the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research. Her research and teaching focuses on how policies can steer and accelerate sustainable energy and mobility transitions.

Emilie Vandam is a member of the Social Innovation Matrix at the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission, and is responsible of the coordination of the European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus within DG R&I. She has a background in history and European affairs. Before joining the European Commission, she worked in the youth and NGO sectors, particularly on citizen engagement. She is a Local Councillor for her town, which allows her to witness and experience citizen engagement and social innovation on the ground.

Cristiana Marchitelli is a member of the digitalisation team and an SSH correspondent at the Directorate General for Energy – Research, Innovation, Digitalisation and Competitiveness Unit. Her focus is on how to empower citizens and consumers in the digitalised energy system of the future. Cristiana studied International Relations at the University of Bologna, Sciences Po Paris, and Johns Hopkins University.

Giorgia Rambelli is the Coordinator, Climate Policy and Energy Governance at ICLEI Europe, and works for the Secretariat of the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, as well as being a part of the European Covenant of Mayors Office. She is involved in the development and implementation of several European projects, drafts positioning documents on climate and energy policy, and provides expert contributions to Opinions for institutions such as the Committee of the Regions, and the European Economic and Social Committee.

Dimitris Tsekeris is the Climate Justice & Energy Campaigner for Friends of the Earth Europe and the Coordinator of the European Community Power Coalition. He is also a member of an energy community. He has been involved in the energy and climate sector for the past years within NGOs and other organizations. He is a mechanical engineer (MEng) specialized in Sustainable Energy (MSc).

Stavroula Pappa is an EU-qualified lawyer registered at the Athens Bar Association. As a Project Manager at REScoop.eu, she represents the Federation in European projects that: design enabling frameworks for energy communities in EU Member States; gain better understanding of storage solutions; and explore how citizens and energy communities can take a more active role in the energy system. Stavroula is involved in screening policy framework conditions, making policy recommendations, researching energy communities that provide storage solutions, facilitating exchange with relevant actors in the energy system, and supporting the communication and dissemination of project results. She actively contributes to the Federation's advocacy work.

8 FURTHER INFORMATION

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ⁱ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_21_3541, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/package-fit-for-55>

ⁱⁱ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/european-green-deal/2030-climate-target-plan_en

ⁱⁱⁱ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions, 'Fit for 55': delivering the EU's 2030 Climate Target on the way to climate neutrality, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0550>.

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PART 2: EVENT REPORT

SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY MEETS THE 'FIT FOR 55' PACKAGE

Policy opportunities and challenges

EVENT REPORT Breakfast at Sustainability's 14 January 2022

Version: 1.0

February 2022

Authors: Maria Stadler, Annalena Broich and Karoline S. Rogge

Illustrations: Carlotta Cataldi

Panel presentations

Tessa de Geus (DRIFT) kicked off the policy dialogue on behalf of the SONNET organising team, welcoming participants and panellists, and presenting the agenda. Adrienne Kotler (ICLEI Europe) provided information about ICLEI, the *Breakfast at Sustainability's* event series, and the composition of the audience.

The following seven speakers contributed to the policy dialogue:

- Julia Wittmayer (DRIFT)
- Karoline Rogge (Fraunhofer ISI; University of Sussex)
- Emilie Vandam (European Commission, DG Research and Innovation)
- Cristina Marchitelli (European Commission, DG Energy)
- Giorgia Rambelli (ICLEI Europe)
- Dimitris Tsekeris (Friends of the Earth Europe)
- Stavroula Pappa (REScoop.eu)

Figure 2-1: Graphic harvest of the presentations given at the policy dialogue Illustration (and its component parts, displayed in the pages that follow): Carlotta Cataldi

Research perspectives: Two SONNET researchers set the scene by highlighting the diversity of social innovation in energy, and illustrating how policy mix thinking can inform discussions about how to better consider social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package.

- **Julia Wittmayer** introduced social innovation, its plurality of definitions, as well as its history in EU-level policy making. For her, a central question is *whether and how social innovation contributes to changing social relations around energy*. Julia highlighted that what is new (i.e. the object of change) in such innovations is social – namely renewed, new or reinvented practices, relations or ideas – and provided SONNET's definition of social innovation in energy as a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy. Based on this broad definition, she presented the different types of social innovation in energy that SONNET has identified, which differ in the ways in which they contribute to changing social relations. This highlights the role that different actors (such as policy makers, businesses, citizens, etc.) play in social innovation in energy. Acknowledging the diversity of social innovation in energy also provides insights into the need to reflect on what kinds of social innovations in energy can and should be supported by the Fit for 55 package¹.

¹ This refers to the European Union's planned "revision of its climate, energy and transport-related legislation" in order to ensure that such policies are aligned with the EU target of reducing emissions by at least 55% by 2030, and reaching climate neutrality by 2050. For more information, visit: consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/green-deal/eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/.

- **Karoline Rogge** presented a 'policy mix thinking' approach to looking at social innovation in energy, describing the Fit for 55 package as an example of applying policy mix thinking to EU energy and climate policy. A 'policy mix' includes a policy strategy and instruments to implement this strategy. To reach the more ambitious Fit for 55 targets for 2030, it is important to ensure that the instruments in the mix are tightened and thus made consistent with the target. Research conducted as part of the SONNET project shows how different types of social innovations in energy are affected by different instruments across different policy fields and governance levels. To fully grasp the potential of social innovation in energy, and to design policy instruments that promote diverse types of innovations, it is important to identify the policy fields and instruments that matter. Furthermore, policy mix thinking acknowledges the political nature of the policy-making processes involved in designing policies that promote social innovation. She concluded that the impacts of policies on social innovation in energy should be monitored as part of policy evaluation so as to generate evidence, which can contribute to redesigning policies for social innovation in the future.

Policy perspectives: reflections on **opportunities** for better consideration of social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package, and **challenges** that could act as barriers to considering social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package.

- According to **Emilie Vandam**, the recent European research programme [Horizon Europe](#) understands social innovation as a cross cutting issue. While social innovation may not be directly mentioned in the Fit for 55 package as such, it is indirectly addressed. She sees making policy-makers aware of social innovation as a major **challenge**. Another challenge is to upscale and replicate social innovations that are often being developed at local level. Furthermore, to replicate and upscale social innovation, it is crucial to convince all policy makers from all levels about the benefits of such innovation. This, however, also links to **opportunities**: technology alone cannot be the answer to challenges like climate change, because such challenges require changes in social practices and behaviours. Social innovation can achieve that and give people a sense of agency. This underlines the need for a mix of technological and social innovation. According to her, the Fit for 55 package can be seen as a great opportunity for social innovation to achieve climate goals while addressing social needs.

- **Cristiana Marchitelli** described social innovation as an approach that enables citizen engagement, helps to overcome trust issues and contributes to a human-centric energy transition. This links to **opportunities** presented by social innovation in energy: they allow for inclusion of citizens from the beginning, listening to citizens' needs and gaining knowledge about how to address and support people. Social innovation in energy can help to inform policy making, create trust and overcome the digital divide. The **challenges** she identified around including social innovation in the Fit for 55 package lie in how difficult it can be to raise awareness among policy makers of the potential of social innovation, especially as it remains unclear how social innovation can be sustained over time. According to her, it is important to create synergies between policies, such as ensuring that a digital transition supports the energy transition.

Practitioner perspectives: reflections on **opportunities** for better consideration of social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package, and **challenges** that could act as barriers to considering social innovation in energy in the Fit for 55 package.

- **Giorgia Rambelli** highlighted the important role that local governments can play in connecting policy making with citizens. Regarding the Fit for 55 package, local governments can, for example, play a proactive role in: bringing forward climate action plans; reassessing plans, adjusting and measuring targets locally; implementing appropriate policies or new initiatives; and acting as testbeds for innovations. She identified several **opportunities** for social innovation in energy to support vulnerable communities, advance gender equality, reduce energy poverty, and enable new forms of collaboration between actors. The **challenges** she identified are speeding-up the energy transition, and making better use of data to quicken and understand its impacts on the ground.

- Dimitris Tsekeris** highlighted the high acceptance of energy communities and renewables across Europe, with 86% of Europeans supporting new wind and solar projects in their local area and 79% of Europeans wanting their government to provide more financial support for renewables (see: cross-EU polling on renewable [energy](#)). From this perspective, there are many **opportunities** that social innovation in energy can bring to the Fit for 55 package, and ways in which energy communities can contribute and play a role in it. Energy communities can help to speed-up the energy transition through democratic participation, reduce energy poverty, increase energy efficiency, increase the acceptance of renewable energy and contribute to solidarity and social justice. Legal barriers in the Renewable Energy Directive ([RED II](#)) present **challenges**, as they can turn energy communities into competitors. Additional challenges lie with the proposed EU taxonomy that labels nuclear and gas energy as 'green'. With social inequalities rising, and 10% of richest responsible for 49% of CO₂ emissions, more political will for change is needed.

- **Stavroula Pappa** identified potential for energy cooperatives to help people at the local level by engaging with local community and energy projects and driving social innovation. According to her, the **opportunities** of energy cooperatives and citizen participation across the EU were identified in the [clean energy package](#) and are now further acknowledged in the Fit for 55 package. Two directives ([EED](#) and [EPBD](#)) recognise the potential of energy communities. However, to really build out the role of energy communities, the directives need to be more precise and to have stronger language. This displays some of the **challenges** she saw with the Fit for 55 package. Namely, recognition of energy communities is not yet backed-up by supportive policies, even though they are much needed, both at the EU- and the national-levels. Another risk emerges around gas energy communities that were introduced with the Commission's proposal for the Gas Directive – these provisions should prevent such energy communities from being 'hijacked' by larger gas companies.

Fishbowl discussion

The subsequent Fishbowl discussion – moderated by Tessa de Geus (DRIFT) – was informed by questions collected via the online tool Mentimeter. Participants asked questions anonymously, and voted for the questions that they would most like to see discussed. The subsequent discussion has been synthesised into five main topics; the order of the responses in this report does not follow the chronological order of the discussion (for which the reader can refer to the event video).

First, **tacking stock of existing forums**, the panellists discussed opportunities to include social innovators in EU decision-making processes. The question for the discussion was formulated as follows: “*What forums do we have to concretely (actually!) bring social innovators and local leaders into the EU decision-making process?*”

- **Cristina Marchitelli** mentioned that there are currently no new platforms being developed, but existing platforms already allow for citizen participation on the EU level. Examples include the [Climate Pact initiative](#), the citizen panel at the [Conference on the Future of Europe](#), initiatives as part of the European Year of Youth and the [European Youth Energy Network](#).
- **Emilie Vandam** additionally mentioned networks among social innovators linked with the European Commission that emerged as part of projects funded in the EU's H2020 framework, such as the '[social innovation community](#)'. One challenge of such project-funded networks is to keep them up when funding stops. Also, at the heart of the New European Bauhaus lies the aim of bringing diverse actors together, following a quadruple helix approach. This also invites social innovation actors to join. Finally, the [R&I days](#) organised by DG R&I allow for citizen contributions.
- **Stavroula Pappa** highlighted the opportunities for exchange and participation that exist as part of the REScoop.eu network, e.g. through

internal working groups and the community power coalition as a forum that enables participation.

- **Giorgia Rambelli** argued for the importance of already existing networks to scale-up initiatives, share knowledge across Europe, and reach beyond innovations on the ground, citing the Covenant of Mayors. One opportunity for networking that she mentioned was the newly launched [European Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities](#)

Second, the importance of strengthening a **shared understanding of the term ‘social innovation’** was discussed. This was linked to the question addressed directly to Emilie Vandam and Karoline Rogge: “*You criticize that SI is not explicit in Fit for 55, but specific forms of it are. Could you elaborate which benefits you see to label these explicitly as SI?*”

- **Emilie Vandam** argued that using the term ‘social innovation’ would contribute to awareness-raising. It would acknowledge the contribution of social innovation and do justice to it. In many cases, people working on social innovation would often not recognise their work as such. Furthermore, using the term would allow policy makers to include it in future policy proposals.
- **Karoline Rogge** emphasised that, especially in the field of energy, the notion of innovation as technological development still dominates. Mentioning social innovation could contribute to shifting mind-sets of people working in the energy sector and remind them that both technological and social innovation are needed for a successful socio-technical transition. Furthermore, mentioning social innovation, rather than just specific types of social innovation in energy, would better acknowledge its diversity and may provide more opportunities for novel forms of social innovation in energy to emerge.
- **Stavroula Pappa** agreed that more specific wording shows acknowledgment and furthermore gives a strong signal to different Member States regarding the implementation of EU policies on a national level.

Third, and linked to the previous question, the **expectations towards social innovation in energy** were discussed, guided by the questions: “Are the expectations of social innovation as a tool not too high? And shouldn't we rather be more critical and conscious about the limitations of the generalisation of social innovation?”

- **Giorgia Rambelli** argued that this very much depends on the underlying understanding of social innovation. From the perspective of local governments, there would be great further potential – not only for innovation on the ground but also in terms of new governance frameworks that strengthen the role of local governments across governance levels. The expectation might be high, but so is the potential that lies in changing our thinking around how to implement energy transitions on the ground.
- **Emilie Vandam** added that there is a need to break down specific aspects of social innovation in different policy fields. This would allow acknowledging their potentials to overcome societal challenges, while staying realistic. She also stressed that we cannot solve everything with social innovation, but need to combine different approaches.
- **Cristina Marchitelli** further elaborated on the need to reduce barriers so that the outcomes of social innovation can be fully grasped or sustained over time. According to her, it is important to understand the ways governments on different levels can be included in designing policies through a social innovation lens. She describes thinking about social innovation as a self-sustaining ambition – if we push the ambition now, we can push even further next time.
- **Dimitris Tsekeris** emphasised that social innovation should not be understood as a tool, but rather as a process. The benefits of including different perspectives in processes would be clearly visible (e.g. leading to greater effectiveness), and he warned of the consequences when these potentials are not recognised.
- **Stavroula Pappa** highlighted the need to back-up existing initiatives with legally binding EU policies to strengthen the position of socially innovative

initiatives in all countries in Europe. Otherwise, social innovation will stay at a more theoretical level.

Fourth, the metrics that exist to gather **data on social innovation in energy** were discussed. The question was: “What type of metrics could we introduce to gather better data on SI impacts in the energy sector? Data are important to policy makers and attract attention”.

- **Dimitris Tsekeris** described different indicators that could be used to keep track of SI-based initiatives, for example changing levels of energy poverty, data on the adequacy of the building stock, income levels, the penetration of renewables, long-term unemployment rates, and more. According to him, the main question is *what metric could reflect the impact of energy communities (over time)*. Concerning further potentials of social innovation, [a recent poll by European Climate Foundation](#) showed that 61% of people would be willing to participate in energy communities. Furthermore, when projects are successful, acceptance of renewable energies and energy communities increases.
- **Stavroula Pappa** reported from a survey and mapping conducted by REScoop.eu and two other organisations on the [social impact of energy communities](#). This was complemented by a workshop with experts in the field, and the aim of the mapping was to develop indicators for the social impact of energy communities. This project focusing on the social impact of energy communities is still under development and more results are expected.
- **Karoline Rogge** shared insights from the SONNET project on this question. The project gathered data from different types of social innovation in energy and analysed whether the goals of socially innovative initiatives align with EU policy goals. However, in particular quantitative data availability was a key issue, with differences in its availability across different types of social innovation in energy. She concluded that gathering data on the rich diversity of social innovation in energy and its various impacts remains a challenge and that so far it is still unclear who is responsible for this.

- **Cristina Marchitelli** added that data gathering would also be done by the [Joint Research Centre \(JRC\)](#), the European Commission's science and knowledge service based on EU-funded projects. The analysis included the topic of social innovation, behavioural changes and the impact of the project on energy issues (e.g. reducing energy poverty, involvement of energy communities, etc.). The data would also feed into further policy-making.

Finally, the discussion closed with a question on further steps and especially **how to get those writing the Fit for 55 energy and climate policy proposals** to adequately consider social innovation: “*What can be done (by whom) to get the penholders on board with social innovation?*”

- **Emilie Vandam** argued that the best way to do so is by raising awareness through concrete examples and the sharing of success stories. This would demonstrate what social innovation can actually achieve.
- **Stavroula Pappa** mentioned the need to actively participate in policy making and to push for amendments and revisions, both at the European level and at national levels. Especially on the national level, it is particularly important to reduce regulatory barriers.
- **Giorgia Rambelli** emphasised that it would be crucial to foster shifts in mind-sets around the importance of acting together in the same direction. From a practical point of view, on the national level it is important to pass on the message that consultations need to happen together with local and regional governments and communities – not only in the planning and implementation of policies, but also in their roll-out, available funding mechanisms and access to different resources.

Status quo reflection of the discussion

After sharing the graphic harvesting of the event (produced by **Carlotta Cataldi**, see Figure 2), the panel closed with a final round of reflections by all the speakers:

- **Cristina Marchitelli** concluded that the ambition to further push social innovation has to be understood as a self-fulfilling prophecy. The higher the ambition is, the more social innovation is integrated into policy-making, the more impactful it will be and the more we could get out of it. *“If we don't bring the impact to the surface and fully grasp the benefits of social innovation, this cannot happen.”*
- **Dimitris Tsekeris** emphasised that the work on social innovation needs to be advanced. According to him, a clear pathway is needed and actors must work together on the shared goal of further acknowledging social innovation in energy. *“We need to be more ambitious to fight the climate crisis and find new ways of collaborating to do so.”*
- **Giorgia Rambelli** highlighted the danger of falling into the trap of thinking that innovation is purely technological. This must not be the case. Regarding local governments, rethinking and reframing cities' roles in transitions, as well as their responsibilities and abilities to work together with communities, is necessary to meet the objectives of the Paris Agreement. *“We cannot reach the goals of the Paris Agreement and make the changes that are needed without including all actors.”*
- **Emilie Vandam** closed with the positive conclusion that things are starting to move in the right direction. Policies increasingly allow leaders to make the changes that are needed, e.g. local governments are more and more participative. *“We are heading towards really interesting times with many social, as well as technological innovations that are currently emerging.”*
- **Stavroula Pappa** highlighted that many people on the ground are interested and motivated to contribute to the transitions needed. As there are still barriers in many countries, backing this up with supportive policies provided by the EU is crucial. *“It is time for people to claim their energy rights and push for better legislation.”*

Figure 2-2: Graphic harvest of the Q&A session at the policy dialogue

Illustration (and its component parts, displayed in the pages that follow): Carlotta Cataldi

PART 3: REFLECTIONS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 837498.

SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY MEETS

THE 'FIT FOR 55' PACKAGE

Policy opportunities and challenges

REFLECTIONS

Version: 1.0

February 2022

Authors: Karoline S. Rogge, Maria Stadler, Tessa de Geus and Sabine Hielscher

Illustrations: Carlotta Cataldi

Social innovation in energy transitions (SONNET): Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

Preface

This reflections document puts forth policy recommendations and needs, as distilled during a multi-level policy dialogue, follow-up validation workshop with cities, and through complementary research. Its recommendations focus on a central tenet: social innovation is crucial to achieving sustainable and just energy transitions in Europe, and thus there is a need for such innovation to be better included in European policies, particularly with respect to the Fit for 55 package.

Strategies for enhancing the role of social innovation in energy in EU, national, regional and local energy policy making - reflections

During the policy dialogue, four main priority topics emerged for which we offer big picture reflections for future policy making, particularly at the EU level, but also with relevance for other governance levels (see Figure 1):

- (1) energy and climate policy maker's awareness of, and willingness to engage with social innovation in energy,
- (2) defining and conceptualizing social innovation in energy transitions,
- (3) benefits and impacts of, and metrics for social innovation in energy, and
- (4) multi-level governance and the role of the local level for supporting social innovation in energy.

For each of these priorities, we offer three action points for policy makers – which are also relevant for researchers and practitioners – as a way forward toward better considering social innovation in climate and energy policy making. It is our hope that they can contribute to enhancing strategies that promote social innovation in energy in the design of policies, not only for the Fit for 55 package, but also in other energy, climate and innovation policy processes in Europe more widely, as well as at national and local levels.

These reflections were developed by a team of SONNET researchers, and then validated in a workshop with city representatives from our SONNET partner cities¹. Based on this co-creation workshop, which confirmed the validity of the identified priority areas and action points, each priority area was accompanied by a text box summarising the main discussion points from the viewpoint of cities.

This reflection document closes with additional concrete ideas from the SONNET city partners on how cities can provide opportunities that further social innovation in energy, and what they need from other governance levels to support socially innovative local action for sustainable energy transitions.

¹ The SONNET cities that participated in the workshop include Antwerp (Belgium), Bristol (UK), Grenoble (France), Mannheim (Germany) and Warsaw (Poland).

Figure 3-1: Reflections on enhancing the role of social innovation in energy in policy making

Illustration (and its component parts, displayed in the pages that follow): Carlotta Cataldi

ENERGY & CLIMATE POLICY MAKER'S AWARENESS OF, AND WILLINGNESS TO ENGAGE WITH SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY

One observation at the policy dialogue was that energy and climate policy makers at the EU and national levels seem to lack awareness of, and knowledge about social innovation in energy. As a result, they may also not be aware that there is a connection between their policy field and social innovation. Instead, energy and climate policy makers seem to perceive research and innovation as the main policy domain with responsibility for supporting social innovation in energy. This limits its consideration in energy and climate policy and thereby its upscaling and wider diffusion.

ACTION POINTS:

1. **Raise awareness for social innovation across energy and climate policy makers.**

Policy makers across different policy fields, and thus beyond the research and innovation domain, need to be aware of the connections between their policy field and social innovation in energy. There currently seems to be an awareness gap among EU and national energy and climate policy makers when it comes to social innovation. Researchers, policy makers and practitioners who specialise in social innovation in energy can directly and indirectly contribute to awareness raising by sharing their expertise and insights, for example by building bridges with mainstream energy and climate policy colleagues – something that could be encouraged through the design of research funding calls.

2. **Connect with key policy actors who are drafting energy and climate policy proposals.**

The consideration of social innovation in energy and climate policy in general, and in the Fit for 55 package in particular, could benefit from connecting social innovation researchers, policy makers and advocacy groups with the Fit for 55 “penholders”. Whether intended or not, energy and climate policies such as those included in the Fit for 55 package, impact social innovation in energy.

Explicitly considering such impacts when designing these policies can help to ensure that the resulting policies have an enabling impact on social innovation in energy by design, not by chance. This could happen, for example, by organising exchange meetings between EU penholders (i.e. those with actual decision-making power) and key experts working on social innovation in energy.

3. Adopt policy mix thinking across energy, climate and innovation policies for governing the emergence, upscaling and diffusion of social innovation in energy.

Energy and climate policy makers seem to perceive their colleagues in the field of research and innovation as holding primary responsibility for social innovation, with an eye to experimentation and thus the emergence of social innovations. However, the combination of energy, climate and innovation policies influences the development of social innovation in energy, with energy and climate policies being particularly important for their upscaling and diffusion. In addition, seemingly disconnected policy changes in other policy fields can – whether intentionally or unintentionally – have an impact on social innovation in energy. One clear example of this knock-on effect is the EU taxonomy. This interconnectedness could be made more explicit, for example, by initiating research on such policy interactions across different policy domains and their impact on social innovation in energy.

REFLECTIONS ON THE ACTION POINTS FROM A CITY-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE

City reflections on action point 1: Awareness raising for social innovation in energy among local policy makers seemed to be relevant as well, but to different degrees for different cities. While city representatives confirmed that there is awareness of social problems among local policy-makers, they still saw a need for experts to discuss how to support socially innovative activities with city councils. Even more so, it was argued that national level policy makers should be brought on board, as they were seen as crucial for removing obstacles and providing resources. At the city level, social innovation is also often not identified as such – socially innovative activities are rarely called ‘social innovations’, even if they do fit the concept. Finally, beyond raising awareness, it was stressed that it is also a question of how to make social innovation more popular politically.

City reflections on action point 2: The failure to identify socially innovative activities as ‘social innovation’ was seen as a key obstacle. Some city representatives emphasised that it is also important to approach committed actors, such as associations, experts and pioneers, for social innovation awareness-raising, rather than only targeting elected officials. Another point mentioned was that social innovation is seen as one possible tool for achieving sustainable energy systems.

City reflections on action point 3: City representatives stressed the importance of implementing policies on a day-to-day basis. Social innovation was seen by some as a *tool* for accelerating energy transitions, while others considered it as a *process*, such as actively involving citizens in decision-making about local energy projects. Finally, there was some concern that a focus on innovation – in the sense of developing new solutions – rather than concentrating on the diffusion of concrete, available solutions could stifle the speed at which actions actually need to be taken.

2

DEFINING and
CONCEPTUALIZING
SOCIAL INNOVATION
IN
ENERGY TRANSITIONS

The policy dialogue observed that it may not only be a lack of *awareness*, but also of *understanding* of social innovation and its role in energy transitions, which hampers its consideration in energy and climate policy making. As a complex concept, social innovation may not be well-enough understood yet by energy and climate policy makers. As such, clearly defining social innovation in energy should be a priority. While various definitions exist, these do not currently translate into accurate identification of what qualifies as social innovation, and thus social innovation can be under-recognised in energy and climate policy discourses. Furthermore, there was a perception that policy makers understand social innovation as instrumental and linked to far-reaching social benefits. This may contribute to the trend of social innovation being praised in general, while its upscaling and wider diffusion tends to be neglected in energy and climate policy making.

ACTION POINTS:

4. Sharpen the definition of social innovation in energy used by policy makers.

While the existing plurality of definitions of social innovation in energy are fruitful in academic discourses, for energy and climate policy makers this leads to confusion. Co-creating a clear, uniform and easily applicable definition of social innovation in energy amongst researchers, policy makers and practitioners – and based on the variety of existing definitions – would be a useful step toward a better consideration of social innovation in policy making. This could be accomplished, for example, by co-creation workshops with policy makers, social innovators and researchers.

5. Adopt both a broad definition of social innovation in energy in general, and complementary specific definitions of key types.

A broad definition of social innovation in energy could help to better connect it to political discussions and to mainstream the concept. Its diversity could be better recognised if definitions for specific types of social innovation in energy are also outlined. Providing illustrative examples could be helpful for furthering policy makers' and practitioners' insights into what may constitute social innovation in energy. The SONNET typology² of social innovations in energy may be a useful starting point for this work. Together, these definitions could promote a better understanding of the concept, increase its popularity, and strengthen its consideration in energy and climate policy making.

6. Devise long-term policy strategies specifying the foreseen role of social innovation in energy transitions.

Social innovation in energy would benefit from considering it in long term policy strategies that govern sustainable energy transitions. These should concretely spell out its foreseen role in these transitions, which may also help to clarify the expectation of these innovations' impacts and potential.

² For more information, refer to <https://sonnet-energy.eu/typology/> and Wittmayer et al (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102513>.

REFLECTIONS ON THE ACTION POINTS FROM A CITY-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE

City reflections on action point 4: While agreeing that a clear and simple definition of social innovation in energy would be useful, city representatives were not overly concerned with developing a uniform definition that would be used broadly. Rather, they advocated for a practical approach focusing on outcome-generation on the local level, acknowledging that they would welcome a uniform definition if developed on the European or national level. Finally, definitions of social innovation should not “over-promise”, as these innovations are one important part of local energy transition action plans, but are not sufficient on their own to solve transition challenges

City reflections on action point 5: The importance of providing a simple definition of social innovation that can be understood by local stakeholders was stressed – namely for policy makers or practitioners, including groups like social workers. In addition, accurate definitions for every type of social innovation were not seen as very important by city representatives. Yet, it was mentioned that using the term ‘social innovation’ and clearly naming socially innovative activities as such could be helpful.

City reflections on action point 6: City representatives agreed that it would be good to integrate social innovation into policy strategies and action plans. There was a preference for an embedded approach, rather than adopting a policy strategy only focussed on social innovation. Some reiterated that social innovation should be included as a means (tool), not as an end in itself – in other words, it should not be seen as an inherent “good”, but rather as a tool to achieve more sustainable energy systems. A clear definition was seen as critical to better consideration of social innovation in policy strategies and action plans. A clearer definition was also thought by some to be useful to enable stakeholders to collaborate toward a shared goal within a certain territory.

3 BENEFITS and IMPACTS of, and METRICS FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY

The policy dialogue pointed to the need for more insights into the benefits and impacts of social innovation in energy, and developing metrics to measure this impact. Practitioners shared examples of how they have been measuring impacts, such as by conducting surveys among social innovation initiatives. Policy makers pointed to the availability of R&D funding for social innovation, as well as to the richness of available – but not yet systematically analysed – research data (e.g. conducted by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre) that could be fed into policy making processes.

ACTION POINTS:

7. Take stock and synthesise existing assessment and evaluation practices used to determine the impact of social innovation in energy.

Academic researchers, in collaboration with policy makers and practitioners, should synthesise existing assessment and evaluation practices, and based on this, suggest suitable methodologies for measuring the impact of social innovation in energy. This process should clarify the extent to which these methodologies can be applied to diverse types of social innovation, and which adaptations, additions or alternatives are needed to account for differences. While acknowledging the limitations of creating a unified “most suitable” assessment and evaluation methodology, such a co-creative process complemented by a differentiated approach may encourage standardisation of assessment practices, while safeguarding consideration of the diversity of social innovations in energy.

8. Ensure that future policy impact assessments and policy evaluations incorporate social innovation as one dimension.

Policy makers, consultants and researchers need to acknowledge social innovation as relevant for policy impact assessment and policy evaluations. Therefore, they should apply existing state-of-the-art assessment and evaluation methodologies for social innovation and further advance them – something that will largely depend on requirements within tenders and research calls. It should be explored how such inclusion of social innovation in

impact assessment and policy evaluation – potentially as one aspect within the examination of innovation in general – can be made mandatory and to which extent it can be standardized. An associated question to this process is which actors, organisations and institutions should be responsible for the uptake of novel assessment and evaluation practices.

9. Improve future policy support for social innovation in energy based on evidence from impact assessments and policy evaluations.

Social innovators, researchers and policy makers need to engage in activities to increase the political and administrative will to support social innovation in energy. In other words, improving monitoring, assessment and evaluation methodologies for social innovation in energy will not be sufficient. Political and administrative will to build on such novel evidence is also essential, particularly when redesigning policies and regulatory frameworks to better support social innovation in energy.

REFLECTIONS ON THE ACTION POINTS FROM A CITY-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE

City reflections on action point 7: On a local level, several metrics exist to take stock of social challenges related to energy (e.g. energy use in social housing); however, these do not directly link to measuring social innovation. Such metrics were anyhow not understood by city partners as key to supporting social innovation, which would rather depend on political will and budgets. Evaluation of social innovation was seen as useful in general, but also as potentially very time- and resource-intensive, which is problematic given tight local budgets and limited staff.

City reflections on action point 8: The incorporation of social innovation in future impact assessments and policy evaluations was seen by some city representatives as not necessarily relevant at the local level, and by others as only relevant for particular policies. By contrast, cities that already conduct impact assessment of their activities thought that grouping all available metrics relevant for social innovation might enable them to draw useful conclusions.

City reflections on action point 9: The importance of political will for supporting social innovation in energy was underlined by city representatives. It was argued that the promotion of social innovation lies less in a lack of metrics or evidence of positive impacts of social innovation, but rather in a lack of staff and available budget. Limited political will was seen to be closely connected to a resulting lack of administrative will and capacity. It was questioned whether improved metrics would change this situation.

4 MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNANCE AND THE ROLE OF THE LOCAL LEVEL FOR SUPPORTING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY

A fourth observation from the policy dialogue concerns the importance of multi-level governance and in particular the role of the local level in supporting social innovation in energy. While the policy dialogue focused on the Fit for 55 package, and thus EU energy and climate policies, it was repeatedly acknowledged that other governance levels play a key role in social innovation in energy. The national level has a clear role, including as those responsible for the transposition of EU directives in Member States. However, cities and regions were also particularly highlighted as having a high potential to support social innovation in energy.

ACTION POINTS:

10. Provide clear EU-level guidance for policy makers at other governing levels regarding the role of social innovation in energy transitions.

Agreement on the EU-level on the importance of considering social innovation when designing policies would provide clearer orientation and guidance – both for crafting EU directives and policies, and for their enforcement and transposition at the national level. In particular, it is important to communicate that energy and climate policies are key to supporting the upscaling and diffusion of social innovation in energy across all governance levels.

11. Ensure consistency between EU and national policies relevant for social innovation in energy.

EU policy makers need to ensure that measures promoting social innovation in energy that are included in EU directives are sufficiently transposed in Member States' national energy and climate policies. Such compliance checks would improve consistency between policies on EU and national levels, thereby sending clearer signals to social innovators and better harnessing the full potential of social innovation in energy across all of Europe. A case in point are the provisions for renewable energy communities in the Renewable Energy Directive, which so far have been insufficiently transposed into the national law of several Member States, thereby undermining the achievement of EU policy goals.

12. Include the perspective of cities in EU energy and climate policy making, in acknowledgement of their proximity to socially innovative initiatives in energy.

EU policies should acknowledge and clarify the role of cities and regions in promoting social innovation in energy, including considering expanding their mandates to shape more sustainable energy systems at the local and/or regional level. This should occur in coordination with other governance levels, such as national bodies, to safeguard policy consistency.

REFLECTIONS ON THE ACTION POINTS FROM A CITY-LEVEL PERSPECTIVE

City reflections on action point 10: City representatives highlighted challenges arising from Member States implementing contradictory policies. Some also mentioned that, while their city already has a good grasp of the beneficial role of social innovation for sustainable energy transitions, EU guidance would be much appreciated to improve national-level support of activities on the local level.

City reflections on action point 11: It was largely agreed that more consistency between EU and national level policies is needed and important. Most concern was raised for the national level, which was perceived by some as most often responsible for policies that impede social innovation in energy. In addition, greater cooperation between all governance levels was seen as a helpful avenue. Channelling EU funding for social innovation directly to cities, as the governance level that is most closely connected to citizens' needs, was seen as another promising path.

City reflections on action point 12: Overall, city representatives agreed that more direct integration of cities' perspectives in EU-level policy making would be helpful. However, they also stressed that, for many local authorities, this is nearly impossible due to a lack of staff and budget for such activities. Only a few larger cities may have the ability to directly 'lobby' on the EU level, for example by having an office in Brussels. Therefore, such lobbying often needs to be done by intermediary actors, such as regional networks. Cities should feed their expertise in social innovation in energy to these intermediaries, making them aware of the role of social innovation in energy transitions. Equally, they should inform them of which EU policies matter most for local action and which EU policy changes are needed from a city perspective.

Additional reflections from the city perspective: local actions to create opportunities for social innovation in energy

Below, we offer examples of actions that cities can take to create opportunities for social innovation in energy. This collection is inspired by concrete actions identified by the SONNET cities.

- **Integrating social innovation in local strategies:** Cities can embed social innovation into their local policy strategies, e.g. in mission statements, and in concrete climate action plans. More generally, city experts should keep reminding local level policy makers of the importance of social innovation in energy.
- **Building inclusive local policy making processes:** Cities can adjust policy making processes on the local level to ensure that community organisations and citizens' perspectives are integrated early on. For ongoing dialogue with citizens, it is important that cities have appropriate platforms that enable this exchange. Coordination of activities with regional actors is also helpful.
- **Setting up concrete policy instruments promoting social innovation in energy:** Local administrations can establish concrete instruments that support social innovation, such as a local climate fund for socially innovative projects. Financial resources in particular are needed, and can be targeted quite specifically at concrete social innovations at the city level.
- **Phasing out local support for fossil fuels:** It is important to phase out impeding activities that hinder social innovation in energy. This especially refers to subsidies for fossil fuels. While the majority of these subsidies are managed at the national level, there are still opportunities to phase out such support for fossil fuels on the local level. This may appear politically unpopular, which is why it is important to clearly communicate potential co-benefits of socially innovative activities in energy, such as fighting (energy) poverty.

Finally, city representatives shared thoughts on what cities need from other governance levels to implement local actions that promote social innovation in energy. This is important, as city activities are limited if national and European frameworks impede them.

- **Funding:** Cities depend on financial support from the national and European levels. Such funding can be provided, for example, via research and development support that enables more experiments within cities, or as an extension of existing instruments, such as making interest free loans available to socially innovative projects.
- **Policy changes:** It is crucial to phase out impeding national and EU policies and regulations that hinder the implementation of social innovation in certain areas. Similarly, national policies can be adopted that support social innovation in energy, such as local electricity bills that ensure competitive markets with low barriers to entry for local actors. Addressing the dominance of large electricity and heat suppliers is needed, as these can impede the emergence of social innovations in energy.
- **Clear guidance:** A clearer definition of social innovation that is not overly complex and is easy to use would help cities in their communication activities to raise awareness for social innovation on the local level. More consistency in European guidelines would also be helpful, as difficulties can emerge from contradictions between European and/or national policies (e.g. aspiring to certain economic goals vs. decreasing carbon footprints).
- **Knowledge exchange:** Knowledge exchange between European cities can support activities on the local level. For this, insights from European projects are helpful and should be made more easily accessible. European city networks can play an important role in supporting a coherent discourse around social innovation in energy.

Appendix: EC summary requirements

Changes with respect to the DoA

The deadline of this deliverable was extended by 2 months (originally due: 31 December 2021, postponed to: 28 February 2022) as it builds up on other deliverables (D2.3, D3.3) which were delayed.

The contents of this deliverable reflect the description of the DoA. We have upgraded the deliverable by extending its audience beyond SIE-initiatives and SIE-intermediaries, i.e. also including guidance of relevance for policy makers and researchers. Finally, we have chosen to build the foreseen policy dialogue around the EU's Fit for 55 proposal, as it represents a major EU energy and climate policy initiative with high relevance to social innovation in energy.

Dissemination and uptake

The policy dialogue brought together more than 90 participants. SONNET consortium partners as well as members of the panel discussion are disseminating the findings via various channels, including via ICLEI's Breakfast at Sustainability's [event site](#).

Short Summary of results (<250 words)

Social innovation is increasingly being recognised in policy making on different policy levels. However, to develop its full potential it is important to understand how policy strategies and instruments impact diverse types of social innovation in energy. Taking the example of the EU's Fit for 55 package, a policy dialogue discussing the opportunities and challenges of better considering social innovation in energy was organised. Based on this, four main priority topics were derived as particularly relevant for future policy making, particularly at the EU level, but also with relevance for other governance levels: 1) energy and climate policy maker's awareness of, and willingness to engage with social innovation in energy, 2) defining and conceptualizing social innovation in energy transitions, 3) benefits and impacts of, and metrics for social innovation in energy, and 4) multi-level governance and the role of the local level for supporting social innovation in energy. For each of these priorities, three action points for policy makers, researchers and practitioners are suggested as a way forward for better considering social innovation in energy and climate policy making.

Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable.

